

**SCIENTIFIC RELATIONS OF THE UZBEKISTAN SSR WITH WESTERN
EUROPEAN AND AMERICAN COUNTRIES (IN THE 60S-80S OF THE 20TH
CENTURY)**

Sarvar Akhmedov, a PhD student at Karshi State University

Abstract: This study covers the history of scientific, technical and cultural relations between scientific institutions and scientists of the Uzbek SSR with Western European and American countries in the 60s-80s of the 20th century. The article analyzes the contribution of Uzbek scientists to the integration of world science in the fields of exact, natural and humanitarian sciences, despite the ideological restrictions of the former Soviet system and the conditions of the "Cold War", based on archival sources. The importance of international congresses, projects within the framework of UNESCO and programs for the exchange of scientists is revealed.

Uzbek SSR, Western Europe, USA, scientific relations, Academy of Sciences, scientific and technical revolution, "Cold War", international cooperation, oriental studies, nuclear physics.

Keywords: Uzbek SSR, Western Europe, USA, scientific relations, Academy of Sciences, scientific and technical revolution, "Cold War", international cooperation, oriental studies, nuclear physics.\

The second half of the 20th century, especially the 1960s-1980s, is characterized in the history of mankind as the period of the World Scientific and Technological Revolution (STR). During this period, science transcended national boundaries and acquired a global character. Although this period went down in history as the Cold War and the confrontation between two major ideological blocs, scientific and cultural ties served as an important means of overcoming political barriers.

From this point of view, it is extremely important to study the history of scientific cooperation of the Uzbek SSR with Western European and American

countries (USA, FRG, France, Great Britain, etc.). During this period, the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan and leading higher educational institutions were able to demonstrate their scientific potential not only on the Union scale, but also on the international stage. The achievements of Uzbek scientists in such fields as oriental studies, archeology, nuclear physics, geology, cotton growing, and chemistry attracted the attention of Western colleagues.

In 1962, 14 scientists from the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR participated in international scientific conferences. For example, Academician S.V. Starodubtsev participated in the international scientific symposium on the problems of deformation in solids in Venice, A.P. Ibrohimov spoke at the international congress on the effects of radiation in England, and Academician H.F. Fozilov at the 19th International Conference on Electrical Systems in Paris¹.

In the 1960s, Vice President of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR, Y.Kh. Turakulov, participated in the II International Congress on Endocrinology in Denmark. He also went on a scientific trip to France, where he got acquainted with the scientific research work of scientists such as J. Roche, R. Michel and S. Lisitsky, who were conducting research in this field with the Laboratory of Biochemistry of Thyroid Hormones. In addition, academicians of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR, H.M. Abdullaev, S.V. Starodubtsev, F.A. Mavlonov, T.N. Koriniyazov, H.F. Fozilov, I.M. Muminov, S.S. Kanash, H.S. Sulaymonova, A.Yu. Yunusov, T.Z. Zohidov, S.A. Azimov, members of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR H.U. Usmonov, S.S. Sodikov, V.P. Shcheglov, O.M. Akramkhozhaev, K.S. Akhmedov, F.N. Rusanov and many other scientists of the republic participated in the work of many international scientific forums, gave lectures and went on scientific trips to foreign countries².

In July 1975, the II meeting of the USSR-Sweden Commission on Scientific and Technical Cooperation was held in Moscow. The meeting was attended by 30 members. Uzbekistan played an important role in this cooperation. In Uzbekistan, the

¹ Садикова Г. УзССР в международных научно-технических связях СССР // Общественные науки в Узбекистане, 1974. –С.5.

² Абуталипов Ч. А. Ўзбекистоннинг халқаро алоқалари. – Тошкент: Ўздавнашр, 1984. – Б.154.

companies "Cisa-Tel" and "Sandoz" in cooperation with local organizations carried out joint activities on chemical protection of cotton and agricultural crops³.

In 1980, an international symposium of mathematicians was held in Urgench on the topic "Algorithm and its application in modern mathematics." The symposium was attended by scientists from Great Britain, Holland, Germany, Switzerland, Austria and the USA. This scientific forum was dedicated to Muhammad Khorezmii, a 9th-century mathematician and astronomer, the founder of the science of algebra, who for the first time systematized the basic mathematical laws known at that time and gave them a practical direction⁴.

In accordance with the intergovernmental agreement on scientific cooperation between the Union and France, in April 1987, Sh.A. Egamberdiev, a research fellow of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR, visited the University of Nice for 3 months. Together with French researchers, the scientist carried out work on the commissioning of a solar telescope, which was planned to be installed in the first quarter of 1988⁵.

Women scientists in the field of medical science also actively participated in relations with foreign countries. For example, in 1973, Professor N. Dehkankhodjaeva participated in the IV International Congress held in Clermont-Ferrand, France, in September 1973, and gave a lecture on the topic "New data on the biology and photophysiology of lamblia⁶."

In conclusion, As a result of a comprehensive study of the history of scientific relations of the Uzbek SSR with Western European and American countries in the 60s-80s of the 20th century, the following important scientific conclusions were made:

3 O'zMA, R-837-fond, 41-ro'yxat, 3904-ish, 82-varaq.

4 Пулатов Х. П., Сулайманов К. С. Участие УзССР в научно-технических связях СССР с капиталистическими странами (60-70-е годы) // *Общественные науки в Узбекистане*, 1987. – №.8. – Б.63.

5 O'zFA MA, 1-fond, 1-ro'yxat, 4473-ish, 24-varaq.

6 Сиддиқов Ш. *Фан элчиси*. Тошкент: Фан, 1976. – Б.39.

GLOBAL CONGRESS ON EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH AND FUTURE SKILLS

In the period under consideration, international scientific cooperation of the Uzbek SSR developed within a strict ideological and political framework set by the Union Center (Moscow). Despite the "Cold War" and the contradictions between the two systems, the "detente of international relations" in the 70s and the "perestroika" policy in the second half of the 80s opened up wider opportunities for the republic's scientists to establish direct contacts with Western scientific centers. In the 60s-80s, the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan and leading higher educational institutions (for example, Tashkent State University) became centers with great scientific potential. The achievements of scientists from the republic in the fields of nuclear physics, solar energy utilization, geology, bioorganic chemistry, cotton growing, and breeding have aroused great interest among scientists from developed countries such as the USA, Germany, France, and Great Britain. This has ensured that scientific cooperation is mutually beneficial.

